

Correlation Between Private School Teachers' Participatory Role In Decision Making And Productivity In North Central, Nigeria

Yusuf, Abubakar Habibat¹

Yusuf.ha@unilorin.edu.ng

+2348034825291

Sheu, Adaramaja Muritala

¹Department of Educational Management
Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

²Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education, Kwara State University, Malete

Abstract

This study examined teacher participatory decision making and productivity in North Central private basic schools, Nigeria. The research design employed for the study was a descriptive survey research method design. The population of the study comprised of 31,566 teachers during the 2022/2023 academic session in all private junior secondary schools in North Central geo-political zone of Nigeria were considered as a suitable population for this study. A multistage sampling technique of stratified, proportionate and convenience sampling were used to select 284 teachers in private schools from 3 States (FCT, Kwara and Niger States) in the zone as participants for this study from the target population. One main and four operational hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The Teacher Participatory Decision Making and Productivity Questionnaire (TPDMPQ) was tested for reliability using test-retest method while Spearman rank correlation coefficient statistics was used to analyze the data and test for hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. From the findings obtained in this study, it was revealed that positive relationship exists between participatory decision making and teachers' productivity, teachers' participation in curriculum management had the highest mean. However, teachers' participation in decisions on school finance had the lowest mean and there is also no significance relationship between school plant maintenance and teachers' productivity. This reveals that, less attention was given to teachers' involvement and effective participation in decisions on maintenance of school plants and school finance. The study concludes that teachers' participation in school policy implementation, maintenance of school plants, curriculum management and school finance all have important roles in improving teachers' productivity. It was recommended that teachers should be actively involved in school policy planning and its implementation including formulation of rules and regulation, late arrival of students and disciplinary policies to improve teachers' productivity and learning outcomes for students.

Keyword: Policy plan, school plant, curriculum management, school finance, teacher productivity

Introduction

The school system is a complex institution with various ways and approaches that can lead to the performance of a distinct task, the success or failure of any school is largely dependent upon the groups that make it up and make decision, effective utilization of the intellectual abilities of these group or human resources helps the development of such school. Teachers are one of the important inputs in the school system (Kaikai & Haruna, 2022). Although other stakeholders like parents, non-teachers, school administrators and the community also take part in the decision making but teachers are actively involved in school activities and programs, their impact in decision making in school cannot be over emphasized unlike other stakeholders. Abdulrahman (2016) affirmed that the stakeholders of any institution are all the people, who have a legitimate interest in the continuing effectiveness and success of that institution. It is pertinent to state that teacher is a central figure in the school operations. They are the closest to students, always in touch with them, more aware of their needs of the students and in a better position to anticipate the effects of decision implementation. In addition, teacher participation in decision making has been shown to be one of the key characteristics of their performance and schools' effectiveness (Wadesango, 2016; Daramola, Ogunsanwo, & Adebayo, 2021).

Teacher productivity on the other hand is the hall mark of school growth and development. Teachers' productivity may be measure in terms of teacher's performance. Afolabi & Aragbaye (2022). Wainaina, Iravo and Waitutu (2014) suggest that

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

teachers' productivity may be evaluated in terms of what the teacher control and actually do in class room such as teaching effectiveness and class room performance. Productivity of staff depends on the extent to which the teacher efficiently utilizes the education input to maximize output. Education input in this regard are resources used in the process of educating a child such as pre-student expenditures, student-teacher ratios, teacher education, experience, salary, school facilities, and administrative factors. This is the more reason why the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014) captures that no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers. Without efficient and effective teachers, the education system will be crippled. Productivity of teachers at work is the most pivotal factor among educational factors as a requirement for teachers to plan, execute and monitor each single educational activity for the sake of school goal.

However, it is important to review the contributions of other authors, researchers and experts in this area of study with a view of drawing from their opinions, observations and recommendations as it affects teacher participatory decision making and their productivity at work. Within the framework of Theory Y, McGregor (1960) emphasized the importance of participative management as a means to tap into the potential and capabilities of employees. It is believed that involving employees in decision making and giving them autonomy and responsibility can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction, productivity, and organizational performance. This theory assumes that employees are self-motivated, enjoy work, and are capable of self-direction and self-control. McGregor suggests that management should create a work environment that nurtures employee potential and allows for greater employee involvement in decision-making processes. Participative decision making aligns with Theory Y, as it encourages employees to contribute their innovative ideas, expertise, and perspectives when making decisions that affect their work. Participative decision making fosters a sense of ownership, responsibility, and empowerment in teachers, as they are directly involved in shaping the decisions that affect their work and the school as a whole. This approach not only increases teachers' satisfaction and motivation but also tap into the diverse knowledge and experiences of the workforce, leading to better decision outcomes and improved educational performance.

Meanwhile, decision making has been observed by Adham (2011) to be the heart of administrative process and leadership in schools needed for the growth and survival of any school. It is a conscious and deliberate resolve that binds the individual or group to take action in a specific way in the effort towards having better result. In schools, Olorunsola and Olayemi (2011) submit that participatory decision making permits the teachers to lend their voice in school matters for the purpose of enhancing their job performance and achieving educational set goals. From their submission therefore, it could be said that teacher participation in decisions were geared towards solving immediate school problems and in the long run aimed at achieving education goals and objectives. These decisions could bother on school instructional programs, transportation systems, personnel administration, staff welfare, student discipline, school plant maintenance, health facilities, admission policy, school finance, extracurricular activities and many others.

Statement of the Research Problem:

Researches have shown over the years that participatory decision making often lead to more efficiency and high staff morale (Wadesango, 2010; Sarafidou & Chatziioannidis, 2013). In spite of this, there has been a lot of controversy as to whether teachers should participate in the decision making or not. In the past, only the school heads engage in decision making, teachers seemed to be neglected by their school heads who managed the schools authoritatively and became unapproachable to the class teachers. They have always been left out when it comes to restructuring the context within which teaching occurs especially on issues related to pedagogy, administration and governance (Abdulai & Shafiwu, 2014). Teachers seemed inefficient and less effective on the job which could be as a result of the fact that they no longer take their job seriously due to non-participation in the management of their schools. Such teachers appeared to shed their responsibilities and did not do much teaching in the schools which seemed to have adverse effect on their students academically. Many students were observed to be poor academically and morally. Students' inadequacies appeared to result from their teachers' poor attitude to work and low level of productivity. Participation of teachers in decision making is one of the pillars of work performance in schools. However, in spite of this, studies (Macha & Mhagama, 2022; Ngussa & Gabriel, 2017) reveal little or no teacher participation in decision making, as school head do not have good relationship with their teachers in the management of various education matters. This condition has dampened teacher morale and work performance and in turn results to poor academic performance on part of the students. Therefore, this study investigates teachers' participation in decision making process for optimal productivity in North Central Secondary Schools.

Objectives of the study:

The study examined the various ways teachers can take part in the decision-making process in the school and how it influences their job productivity. Specifically, this study

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

1. Determine the correlation between teachers' participation in school policy implementation and teachers' productivity in Private Basic Schools in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
2. Investigate the relationship between teachers' participation in maintenance of school plant and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
3. Determine the relationship between teachers' participation in curriculum management management and their productivity in North Central basic schools, Nigeria.
4. Examine the relationship between teachers' participation in school finance management and their productivity in North Central basic schools, Nigeria.

Hypotheses:

The following hypothesis were postulated and tested in this study:

Main:

There is no significant relationship between teacher role in decision making and productivity in North Central Basic schools, Nigeria.

Operational Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' role in school policy implementation and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' role in maintenance of school plant and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship teachers' role in curriculum management and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.
4. There is no significant relationship between teachers' role in school finance management and teachers' productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive research of the survey method. This design is appropriate for this study because it allowed the researcher from a sample of the population, analyse the data and make reasonable recommendation about the whole population. Furthermore, the quantitative study was considered a correlation between participatory decisions making with regards to teachers' productivity in North Central basic schools. A total number of 31,566 teachers in all private junior secondary schools in North Central geo-political zone of Nigeria were considered as a suitable population for this study (FGN, 2018). A multistage sampling technique of stratified, proportionate and convenience sampling were used to select 284 teachers in private schools from 3 States (FCT, Kwara and Niger States) in the zone as participants for this study.

Following the sample of 284 participants, teachers were selected based on the percentage proportion of the population in each stratum as 25% of the sample teachers were from FCT, 34% from Kwara and 41% from Niger State constitute the sample. This makes up a total of 284 participants. The method then required that teachers be selected using convenient sampling of schools. The instrument developed for this study was in two parts, a structured questionnaire tagged, "Participatory Decision Making and Teachers' Productivity questionnaire (PDMTPQ)". The Part A contains 16 items on a four-point Likert like rating scale of Always (4points), Often (3points), Sometimes (2 points) and Never (1point) respectively to elicit information on participatory decision making and the Part B consist of 10 items for teachers' productivity questionnaire. The instrument was validated by two experts in the Department of Educational Management, University of Ilorin. Their comments and corrections were incorporated and used to finalize the instrument for data collection. For the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha value of 0.76 obtained adjudged the instrument reliable for use in this study. The final instrument was administered to participants and the rate of return was 88% after retrieved ones were checked to ensure the completeness and correctness of data without missing values. This was considered appropriate for analysis using Statistical Package for Social Science.

Results

There is no significant relationship between teacher role in decision making and productivity in North Central Basic schools, Nigeria.

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

Table 1: Teacher Participation in Decision Making and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
Participatory Decision Making	250	2.71	0.89	0.125	0.043	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Work, 2023

Table 1 represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher participation in decision making and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.125, p-value = 0.043 and sample size = 250. Although the Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.125 indicated that there exists a weak positive relationship between teacher participation in decision making and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. However, the p-value indicated that there is a significant relationship between teacher participation in decision making and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. As the teacher participation in decision making increases, their productivity increases by just 13%. P-value = 0.043 is less than level of significance of 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there exists a significant relationship ($p = 0.125 < 0.05$ for a two-tailed test).

Operational Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teacher role in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 2: Teacher Participation in School Policy Implementation and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
School Policy Implementation	250	2.45	1.12	0.513	0.002	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher role in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.513, p-value = 0.002 and sample size = 250. Although the Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.513 indicated that there exists a positive relationship between teacher role in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria, however, the p-value indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between student teacher participation in school policy implementation and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. As the teacher participation in policy implementation increases, their teacher productivity increases by 51%. P-value = 0.002 is less than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teacher role in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 3: Teacher Participation in School Plant Maintenance and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
School Plant Maintenance	250	2.02	.733	0.008	0.077	Accept Ho

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

Teacher Productivity	2.25	0.134
----------------------	------	-------

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher role in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.008, p -value = 0.077 and sample size = 250. The Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.008 indicated that there exists a weak positive relationship between teacher role in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. Therefore, the result implies that as teacher participation in school plant maintenance increases, their productivity increases by 8%. P -value = 0.077 is greater than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is accepted while the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Hence, the results indicated that there is no significant relationship between teacher participation in school plant maintenance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between teacher role in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 4: Teacher Participation in Curriculum Management And Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
Curriculum Management	250	2.32	.820	0.520	0.018	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher participation in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 with p -value of 0.018 and sample size = 250. The Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 indicated that there exists a strong positive relationship between teacher participation in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. Since the correlation obtained with a p -value less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the result reveals that as teacher participation in curriculum management increases, teacher productivity increases by 52%. P -value = 0.018 is less than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the results indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between teacher participation in curriculum management and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

H0₄: There is no significant relationship between teacher participation in school finance and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Table 5: Teacher Participation in School Finances and Teacher Productivity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-Value	Decision
School Finances	250	2.23	1.008	0.520	0.018	Reject Ho
Teacher Productivity		2.25	0.134			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Source: Field Work, 2023

The above table represent the correlation coefficient result of the relationship between teacher role in school finances and productivity. The result indicated that Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 with p -value of 0.018 and sample size = 250. The Spearman correlation result (r) = 0.520 indicated that there exists a positive relationship between teacher participation in

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

teachers' role in school finances and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria. Since the correlation obtained with a p-value less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the result reveals that as teacher participation in school finances increases, teacher productivity increases by 52%. P-value = 0.000 is less than level of significance = 0.05, which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the results indicated that there is a significant positive relationship between teachers' role in school finances and teacher productivity in North Central Basic Schools, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigates the relationship between teachers' role in decision making and teachers' productivity, the raised objectives in the study were analyzed using the correlation table, the findings suggest areas of teachers' participation in school decision which include, school policy implementation, school plants maintenance, Curriculum management and school finance play a vital role in improving teachers' productivity. There exist a significant positive correlation exists between Participatory Decision-Making and Teachers' Productivity. The findings in line with Mashambo, (2022) and Tijani, (2022) that participatory decision making can have a significant positive impact on teachers' productivity, in terms of both their job performance and their engagement with their work. When the teachers are given a voice in decision making and the opportunity to participate in school governance, they are more likely to feel a sense of ownership and engagement with their work. In, participatory decision making can improve communication and collaboration among teachers which can lead to better working relationships and improved teamwork. As a result, teachers may be more productive and may be more likely to stay in their jobs for longer periods of time.

The study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between school policy implementation and teachers' productivity. However, it is important to understand this relationship in context, when teachers are given the opportunity to participate in policy implementation, they are more likely to feel like they are part of the decision-making process and that their voices are being heard. This, in turn, leads to increased job satisfaction and commitment to the school. Giving teachers a voice in policy implementation is not only beneficial for the school, but also for the teachers themselves. Teacher participation in policy implementation can have a positive impact on student achievement. This finding is in line with that of Derrington and Anderson (2020) whose study focused on the roles of teacher participation in school policy implementation.

The study revealed that there is no significant relationship between maintenance of school plants and teachers' productivity. This implies that, less attention was given to teachers' contribution in school plant maintenance for efficient and effective of teachers' productivity and performance, this affects the overall activities of the school in general and teaching-learning process in particular. The findings underscore the importance of school plants and its maintenance. The findings of this study is in agreement with the Jacob and Gupta (2013) studied the influence of physical facilities on teacher performance in secondary schools in urban and rural areas. The study found that teacher satisfaction with physical facilities was significantly related to teacher perceptions of productivity and effectiveness. The findings of this study suggest that teachers should be actively involved in the maintenance of physical facilities of schools such as the school buildings, equipment, textbooks, hostels, laboratory, furniture and school offices, so as to improve teachers' job satisfaction and their productivity.

It was also revealed that there is a significant relationship between curriculum management. Curriculum management includes developing of teaching methodologies, setting learning goals, deciding on the type of instructional material to be used for each topic, evaluating student performance and extra curriculum activities. Teachers have two distinct role to play. One is their role in instruction and their other role is in participating in school management and decision-making. The study revealed a significant relationship between school finance and teachers' productivity, when teachers are given the opportunity to participate in school decision making, it gives them a sense of ownership over the policies and procedures that affect their job. This can lead to increased job satisfaction, as teachers feel that their input is valued and that they have a voice in the decision-making process. It can lead to increased motivation and engagement, as teachers are more likely to feel invested in the success of the school if they have been involved in shaping its policies. It also creates a culture of collaboration and trust among teachers, which can facilitate the sharing of ideas and resources.

Conclusion

In conclusion, these findings indicate that teachers' participation in school policy implementation, Maintenance of school plants curriculum management and instruction and school finance all have important roles in improving teachers' productivity. School heads/ principals should ensure teachers are actively engaged in the decision-making processes of the school for a greater output by the teachers and quality students' performance. From the findings obtained in this study, it was found that positive relationship between participatory decision making and teachers' productivity, teachers' participation in curriculum

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

management and instruction had the highest mean. However, teachers' participation in decisions on school finance had the lowest mean and there is also no significance relationship between school plant maintenance and teachers' productivity. This reveals that, less attention was given to teachers' involvement and effective participation in decisions on maintenance of school plants and school finance. This can affect teaching and learning process in general and the overall activities of the school. Teachers have two distinct roles to carry out. One of their roles is instruction and the other is their involvement in school administration and decision-making processes. The study indicated that teachers participated mostly in decisions regarding curriculum management and instruction. 58 However, from this finding obtained, it can be concluded that there might be a misconception in identifying and understanding teachers' duties and functions by both the teachers, school heads, PTA and educational officials, they might consider teachers duties and functions as teaching and learning activities alone and other activities as the duties and responsibilities of administrators of school. Teachers must have a voice in the decision-making processes of the school and school heads should ensure full participation of teachers in school decision making, so as to enhance their productivity and to provide a quality learning outcome.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Teachers should be actively involved in school policy planning and its implementation including formulation of rules and regulation, late arrival of students and disciplinary policies to improve teachers' productivity and learning outcomes for students.
2. School heads/Principals should ensure that teachers are fully involved in ensuring that school facilities such as library, school buildings, equipment, hostels, laboratories, furniture and so on are well maintained and managed so as to secure school resources and maintain a safe and functional school environment.
3. School Principals should give room for teachers to take part in decision making on deciding teaching methodologies, setting learning goals and objectives, instructional materials, content and forms of lesson plans and extra-curricular activities, for easy implement school curriculum and to meet the needs of all categories of students.
4. Teachers should be given the opportunities to participate in determining school financial process through committees or other structures

Acknowledgements

This study acknowledges the contributions and support of research assistance who has helped in the process of data administration and the cooperation of all sampled private secondary schools across the North Central Geo-political zones in Nigeria.

References

- Abdulahi, I. A. & Shafiwu, A. B. (2014). Participatory decision making and employee performance. A case study of community banks in the upper east region of Ghana (9) 9- 16
- Abdulrahman, A. (2016). Employee participation in decision-making and firm performance. *International Business Research*, 9 (7), 342-365
- Abere, M. A., Daramola, K. O., Ogunsanwo, O. F., & Adebayo, A. O. (2021). Effect of capital market development on economic growth in Nigeria. *Fuoye Journal of Finance and Contemporary Issues*, 1(1), 111-121.
- Adham, A. (2011). Employee involvement and its impact on job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)* 18(2), 368-400.
- Afolabi, C. (2022). Teachers' Participation in Management and Decision Making as Determinants of Teachers' Productivity in Secondary Schools In Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*.
- Afolabi, O. E., Afolabi, O. E., & Aragbaye, M. O. (2022). Information literacy skills, teachers' self-efficacy and use of information resources by secondary school teachers in selected secondary schools in Ijebu Ode Local Government, Ogun State. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e- journal)*, 7001.
- Derrington, M. L., & Anderson, L. S. (2020). Expanding the Role of Teacher Leaders: Professional Learning for Policy Advocacy. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 28(68), 68-82
- Jacob, V. C., & Gupta, P. V. (2013). Influence of attitude, school facilities and teacher characteristics on the performance of secondary school teachers working in rural areas. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 2, 72-81.
- Kaikai, A.H. & Haruna, A.S. (2022). Contribution of School Supervision towards Predicting Secondary School Students' Achievement in History in Northwest States of Nigeria. *Zamfara International Journal of Education*, 2(1), 148-156.

Correlation Between Private ... (Yusuf & Sheu, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401441>

- Macha, E. P. & Mhagama, M. (2022). Teachers' Participation in Decision Making and Work Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Meru District Council in Arusha Tanzania. *Journal of Humanities and Education Development*, 4 (1), 124- 138
- Mashambo, G. G. (2022). *Role of Participative Decision Making on Teacher Job Performance in Public Primary Schools in Mbozi District, Songwe Region* (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).
- Ngussa, B. M., & Gabriel, L. (2017). Participation in decision making and teachers' commitment: a comparative study between public and private secondary schools in Arusha Municipality, Tanzania. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 5(7), 801-807.
- Ogunsanwo, O., & Akinyemi, M. (2016). The effect of participatory decision-making on teachers' productivity in secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 8(1), 45-57
- Olorunsola, E. O., & Olayemi, A. O. (2011). Teachers participation in decision making process in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Administration and Policy Studies*, 3(6), 78-84.
- Sarafidou, J. O., & Chatzioannidis, G. (2013). Teacher participation in decision making and its impact on school and teachers. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 27(2), 129-145.
- Tijani, A. A. (2022). Participatory Decision Making: An Effective Tool for School Effectiveness in Kwara State, Nigeria. HONAI: *International Journal for Educational, Social, Political & Cultural Studies*.
- Wadesango, N. (2010). The extent of teacher participation in decision-making in secondary schools in Zimbabwe. *School Leadership and Management*, 30(3), 265-284.
- Wadesango, N. (2012). The impact of teachers' participation in decision-making on student performance in secondary schools in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 32(1), 13-22.
- Wadesango, N. (2016). The implications of Bourdieu's theory on teaching and learning: key intervention strategies espoused in one South African university. *Journal of Educational Studies*, 15(1), 107- 125.